

The Growing 'Kidfluence' on Parents' Buying Behavior: The Era of Young Consumers

¹Anadi Trikha,²Dr. Kavya Saini,

¹Assistant Professor,²Associate Professor

¹Faculty of Management,

¹Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur, India

²Department of Management Studies,

²International School of Informatics & Management, Jaipur, India

Abstract

The term 'Kidfluence' means the influence that children exert, both directly and indirectly, on the consumer decisions made by their parents. Traditionally we associate adjectives to describe kids as cute, innocent, lovable, naughty, and sweet among others. In our society way back, kids were never treated as consumer and marketers were always focused on adults as their sole targets. The development of consumer socialization at all ages through various mediums today vanished the passive role of kids in the process of purchase decisions made by their parents. Busy lifestyle of parents, easy access to knowledge for children has made them actively involved in family decisions. This paper highlights the trends of parenting nowadays. It has also explored the different connotations with impact of advertising to children. Latest examples of pester power are also mentioned in the paper. This paper examines the growing market of children's products. The paper has highlighted the trends are changing and parents of today encourage children to be the decision makers in family. Marketers are now using the innocence of children to sell to the parents. Kidfluence has started the era of young consumers.

Keywords: Kidfluence, Consumer Socialization, Consumer Behavior, Purchase Decisions, Young Consumers.

INTRODUCTION

Kids' influence that shapes household purchase decisions is described as the term "Kidfluence". Over a decade concerns about growing influences of children over their parents' buying behaviour & purchase choices has been voiced in many researches. In India with more youth and adolescents represent a large part of the market and they influence the parents buying decisions. Family dynamics have changed over past decade.

Dagnaud highlights “How much the family model and, within it, the child’s place, have evolved.” Children have now a greater influence and effect on family buying behaviour. For example desire of an apple electronic gadget is common in teens today. Advertising has majorly contributed towards this “kidfluence” over family purchase decisions. Parents therefore appear to be influenced twice: directly through advertisements and indirectly through their offspring’s’ role. In the 80s ads were directed towards adults, in 90s the target gradually become children. Noticing this change marketer adopted the kids as new target market to influence parents. This consumerist orientation now pervades all aspects of social world in capitalist societies & users of other non-commercial services such as health & education are increasingly positioned as consumers.

Not just marketing but factors like family, peer group helps children in learning how to be consumers. Whether Parents are buying house or a car, today these kids are pursuing their parents with their choices. Parents consider themselves the voice of reason when it comes to making buying decisions, weighing the opinions of the rest of the family and managing purchases. Kids are often the arbiters of what’s cool, serving as the information-gatherers and advocating for specific brands. Advertisements have greatly impacted the minds of these young influencers in the family. These kids have become great sources of information regarding any sort of decisions the parents are about to make. From choices of colours to sizes & prices you ask these kids they give you their firm opinions. Three out of Four parents say kids’ influences their purchase decisions. This paper is examines the various tactics used by marketers to create advertisements which leaves impression on both parents and kids and how collectively they decide to buy that specific product.

In today’s marketing environment, marketers are concentrating on the branding awareness; marketing and most important point is selling of their products because it helps in profit maximization and better branding position in the market. Kids are base for the marketer to influence the parent’s imagination and thought, so that they are highly obliged by their kids to buy any toy or anything which is related to the kids. If we are in any fair to roam around their, we see that many balloon shopkeepers, toy shopkeeper wants to influence and attract the kids. So their parents will highly be obliged to buy such thing to persuade them.

EXPLOITED OR EMPOWERED

From the very first breath today children are consumers. Modern childhood lives in an era of commercialized goods & services. Marketing to these vulnerable kids is not new but today these little alpha kids know their own rights and also influence the parents too. This consumer culture offers opportunities

which they have not enjoyed in past. Yet so far this thought is an urgent social problem which exists in very household today. Politicians, Leaders, Child Welfare Groups have expressed concern over this serious everyday problem. These groups asks the parents to provide a commercial –free environment at home as its evident that this commercialization is becoming a major sources of unhealthy lifestyle of children, eating disorders, promotes inciting conflicts among family & peer groups. The focus of objections is often far from clearly defined. Buckingham in his book has raised questions like whether this issue talks about over-sexualisation of materialistic products, junk food advertising, underage fashion models, accelerate consumerism? What role does parents play when pester power is hard to handle? Many publications have raised opinions on Child Consumer Culture. Few prominent examples include Juliet Schor's Born to Buy: The Commercialized kid and the new consumer culture (2004), Daniel Acuff& Robert Reiher's Kidnapped: How irresponsible marketers are stealing the mind of your children (2005). These books share negative connotation on influence of advertising & marketing on children's lives. Parents are also urged to take responsibility for ensuring their children's educational success. Good Parenting is one of the popular trends seen lately. Most parents today want the kids to spend time in meaning full activities which contributes towards holistic development. Seeing this trend, education publisher, Software companies have started marketing various apps, subscription boxes to target such families. Flinto Box, Cocomokids, First cry's Intellikit, Byjus's & Disney's Early Learning app in few new products available to cater this need of good parenting.

On the positive note few articles on The Times & Marketing Week mentions though the idea of positive pester power seems paradoxical but when we see it in broader term through advertisement Brands encourage positive activities rather than directly promoting themselves. Examples stated above encourage healthy habits among kids. When kids have more knowledge about certain products, decisions taken reap great benefits. Articles have mentioned parent's statement about how they have benefitted from the information kids have given on specific products they wanted to buy and results were very satisfactory.

THE PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP

Majority of such influences have found its place where there is single child or Urban Household or Households with two full-time working parents. Advertising is one of the major factors that contribute to children's shopping & buying behaviour which indeed

plays an important role in their socialization via consumption. It's evident that sixty per cent of kids know the family budget. Pat Spungin has mentioned though pester power exist but there exist parents power. McNeal identified children represents three types of markets, firstly as primary consumers that spend their allowances, pocket money on small treats occasionally, secondly, as influencers on parental spending on big ticket items and thirdly, as future potential adult consumers. For marketers children are of great interest both as primary consumers and as influencers of secondary consumption. Children are little naggers who on average make 15 requests during a shopping visit. Marketers create conflicts situation between parents and child – the secondary marketer they often attempt to influence. In this context “pestering is the most common technique used. With the age and maturity level of kids pester power often comes in various forms, for e.g.: Nagging, Disturbing, Irritating, Promising, Annoying, Teasing etc. The catch here is that kids and parents value purchases that encourage family time, but also have very different motivation. The rational drivers of purchase decisions for Parents are: My Kids Like it & Costs, for kids its: Everyone will like it & it's for Kids.

PRODUCT CATEGORIES INFLUENCED BY KIDS

There are three main product categories' that are of direct interest to most kids: Clothing, Toys & Food & entertainment in Electronic goods for older children. It's very common nowadays to ask the choices of kids before going to a restaurant. Children are mostly accompanied with grocery shopping where they skip everything and enter the kids' aisle, where confectionary items are positioned in a way to attract & trick kids. Researchers have shown here some kids tend to hide items of their choice in parents trolley. Kids buy items which they have seen on TV or in hands of their friends and family. Products with a freebie or gift are hot cakes in kids market.

Britannia's ad for Cheese showcasing a kid showing the benefits of cheese to his mother in a song “Yeh Cheese Badihai mast mastyeh cheese badihai mast” and trying to show that mom is old-school and he knows the benefits and asks his mother to buy him Britannia Cheese.

Advertisements of Honda Car can be seen where kids sit proudly in a Honda Car and smiles at his friends. The person who is the driver shows off all the features of the car, kids feel amazed by sitting n such luxury. This ad at the very same time influence parents mind to give such luxury to their kids and kids mind that they want such luxury. So when parents decide to buy a car these impressions of the advertisements will work in favour of the marketer from both the sides.

Domino's Pizza has a dedicated see through counter for young kids to see the dough preparation and influence the kids' minds that it's in front of us and is prepared in a healthy way. This is again an example which contradicts the opinions of parents who think Pizzas as unhealthy food for their kids.

AshianaUmang Builders promote their apartments through an ad where one flat opens up with lots of energy kids' barge in and start playing and roaming around. The couple the parents sees each other and becomes very happy and confident about their decision when they see the kids extremely happy. The kids come back to the parents and hug them and say "This is my dream home". Again this ad positions happiness of kids into parents mind and happiness of being in such a big house into kids' minds. Above examples are a few to quote, which straight forwardly connecting kids influence over parents purchase behaviour.

EMOTIONAL DRIVERS OF PURCHASE DECISIONS

Psychologists have suggested that there are various emotional factors that play as major drivers in purchase decisions. See Fig

For Kids	For Parents
Spending quality time with family.	Family Time
Being asked in for opinions seems respectful.	Caring for Kids opinions
Being trusted	Becoming kids best friends
Escaping pressure and being a kid	Providing everyday care

Above drivers show how the both the kids and their parents are influenced by the advertiser and marketer of the kids based product manufacturer. Everybody has different work and economic conditions, but these companies make such type of products which will be affordable for the prospective customers. Sometimes the above psychological points gives a way to marketers and advertisers to use these point as marketing of their products to influence the kids due to which their parents will highly obliged to buy such products.

REASONS OF GROWING CHILD CONSUMERISM

Selling Cool

A kid wants their parents to upbeat whatever they have seen their friends or friends parents have been doing. Many times kid wants to imitate their parent's style and their friends' style to satisfy their needs of fun. Whether it's competing with watches, electronic gadgets or even vacations, Marketers have left a message through advertising that whatever you have is nothing and go buy more. Kids have been lied to in their living rooms day after day about being cool and how to show it to others through different gadgets, products & services. Advertiser pays special attention to create a continuous need for products by exploiting children's aspirations, whether for a certain body type, attitude or personality trait.

When a child see kinder joy ad with a gift inside he/she wants it. When ChotaBheem promotes Parle-G Biscuit and becomes strong the kids want it. Cadbury Lickables ads show that aliens can come to earth to eat the chocolate why can't you? Similar ads can be found in all High Sugar and Salt Products sold to children. Diamond Chips, Frito Lays, Bingo Mad Angles, Mc Donald's Happy Meal sell junk food for big profit

margins. Even brands like Lenovo Yoga Laptop, Ceat Tyres Vodafone, Honda Cars, Hamdard Rogan Badam Oil, SBI Mutual Funds, Dettol, DaburChawanprash need kids' innocence's in ads to sell their products.

Branding

Brands exist in our lives, consciously or unconsciously we all are driven by brand identities. Children from their early childhood have been bombarded by brands defined by name products and intrusive and clever advertising strategies. When as adults we are victims of branding, kids are very far from reality. Nestle, Kwality Walls, Vadilal, Disney and Cadbury etc. to name a few are brands kids have been hearing from their parent since childhood. Eventually when these kids grow they will demand such brands as they have approvals of their parents. Children also experience branding through contemporary consumer culture's obsession with celebrity and various other characters associated with brands.

CONCLUSIONS

As generations of children become socialized in consumer cultures their childhood will have been so shortened that many will scarcely remember a time when they were not operating as consumers. Studies have proven the fact that household cannot be studied without children's role in decision making. Children's identities have been intoxicated linked marketers agenda to promote consumptions on the whole. Positive impact of such influence when parents who spend most of the time at jobs feel vulnerable when they don't get to spend enough time with kids spend quality family time with kids, children's viewpoints are given due regards, on the whole everyone becomes happy.

On the other side children are losing their grip on childhood as a result of steady encroachment of media into every aspect of their lives. Study has suggested that whether pestered, powered or whatever parents always check out the product which the kids wants to buy, parents have a good understanding of marketing and promotional packaging pass their views to children and make them understand whether it is good or bad. Parents accept advertising as the reality of consumer society and one cannot dismay the fact. Accepting the fact and guiding the children might help to overcome the negative impacts of advertising to children. Parents play pivotal role in making the kids understand the difference between good and bad and asking them to choose for healthier options available.

Most parents in his study agreed that not always everything kids demand for is bought but it's the role of the parents to make the children understand the difference between 'Need' & 'Want'. Parents do bow down to children's choices but they may not flinch to even say 'No'. There may be negative associations concerning pester power and considers them potentially unreflective of what actually occurs. Limitations of the study were that it was theoretical paper based on previous studies. Scope of this conclusion could be proved if a study on parent-child relationship can be done in Jaipur city.

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